

Solid state conductance in fused ring aromatic compounds

M. Deepak^a, A. Sharan^a, P. Srinivasan^a, K. Shahi^b and K. V. Srinivasan^{b*}

^aMagadh Mahila College, Patna-800 001, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005, India

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Solid state conductance in aromatic fused ring compounds such as naphthalene, anthracene and phenanthrene exhibits space charge limitations. The measurements point to the presence of traps exponentially distributed over a wide energy range. Currents are found to vary with temperature in these samples exhibiting low activation energies. The activation energy decreases from naphthalene to anthracene, but is seen to be more or less similar with increasing number of rings in such polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.

The theory of steady state space charge limited conductance^{1,2} has been applied to study the traps in organic solids. The present study is on naphthalene, anthracene and phenanthrene having partially overlapping π -electron clouds, lying above and below the planes of the molecules. For naphthalene, the measurements of steady state currents at fields ranging from 5 to 12 MV m⁻¹ were taken. The electrode separation was varied from 0.2 to 0.75 mm. Changing of the polarities of the electrodes did not alter the J - V characteristics. Currents through anthracene and phenanthrene discs of thicknesses 400–750 μ m were measured at fields ranging from 0.5 to 5 MV m⁻¹. The current in all these samples was found to increase with temperature. Naphthalene contains flat six-membered rings and the structure provides electron clouds. The carbon atoms lie at the corners of two fused hexagons. Each carbon is attached to two carbon atoms and a hydrogen atom by σ -bonds. Since these σ -bonds result from the overlapping of trigonal sp^2 orbitals, all carbon and hydrogen atoms lie in a single plane. Above and below this plane, there is a cloud of π -electrons formed by the overlapping of p -orbitals. This cloud can be considered to be two partially overlapping sextets that have a pair of π -electrons in common.

For anthracene and phenanthrene, consideration of atomic orbitals follows the same pattern as naphthalene and leads essentially to the same kind of picture with three fused benzene rings instead of two. A flat structure with partially overlapping π -clouds lying above and below the plane of the molecule exists.

Results and Discussion

The electronic conduction in such compounds occur because of the π -electrons they contain. Since the π -electrons are coplanar, a hopping process appears to be favourable where the extra electron can jump from one excited orbit of

one molecule over an energy barrier into a similar orbit belonging to the adjacent one. However, the $\log J - \log V$ curves exhibit a slope between 2 and 3 (Table 1), indicating a continuous distribution of traps in energy. This has been supported in the case of anthracene³

Sample	Thickness μ m	Slope of curves $\log J - \log V$
Naphthalene	500	2.24
	350	2.35
	250	2.28
Anthracene	530	2.23
	410	2.21
	220	2.27
Phenanthrene	440	2.31
	320	2.28
	210	2.22

The low activation energies (0.02–0.06 eV) indicate electron conduction, probably on account of peripheral π -electrons.

In all the above cases, a power law of the form $J \propto V^n$, where $2 < n < 3$, could be fitted to the observations. This suggests a trap exponential energy distribution localised below the conduction band. In amorphous or polycrystalline materials, which are characteristic of thin film insulators, a distribution of trap levels exists rather than a discrete level of traps as suggested by Simmons⁴

Rose⁵ treated the case of space charge limited conduction in the presence of a distribution of trap levels that decreases exponentially in density with increasing energy below the conduction band. He suggested that the prominent characteristics are a consequence of the distribu-

tion of traps in energy and not of strict uniformity of distribution. For a given applied voltage, the charge Q , forced into the insulator, is distributed in three major parts : (i) free charge in the conduction band, (ii) trapped charge above the newly determined Fermi level and (iii) trapped charge, condensed in the states between the original and the newly determined Fermi levels. Rose⁵ made an approximation that the condensed charge is very nearly equal to the total charge. In such a case, the new location of the Fermi level is given by considering all of the charge Q to be condensed. The shift in the Fermi level will be proportional to the space charge, which in turn is proportional to the applied voltage V .

The distribution of trap density¹ in an insulator can be assumed to be

$$H(E,x) = h(E_0,x_0)f(E).g(x)$$

where $h(E_0,x_0)$ is the boundary trap density and $f(E)$ and $g(x)$ are functions describing the energy and spatial distribution respectively, x is the distance measured from the injecting electrode. The dependence of space charge limited current on the characteristic parameters of the solid can be derived by solving Poisson's and the continuity equations,

$$dF(x)/dx = \rho_{t(x)}/\epsilon$$

$$J = \mu \cdot \rho_{f(x)} F(x)$$

where $F(x)$ denotes the total intensity of the electric field, $\rho_{f(x)}$ and $\rho_{t(x)}$ are the densities of the free and trapped charge, μ is the carrier mobility and ϵ the dielectric constant. The free carrier density is

$$n_c = N_c \exp \{-E_f/(kT)\} \exp (\Delta E/kT) \quad (1)$$

where N_c is the no. of states in the bottom of the conduction band, E_f the original distance of the Fermi level from the conduction band and ΔE the shift in the position of the Fermi level owing to the condensed charge Q forced into the insulator by the applied voltage V . Also

$$\Delta E = Q/en_t S = VCl(en_t S) \quad (2)$$

where E is the electronic charge, S the thickness of the insulator and n_t the number of traps per cm^3 per unit range in energy. From eqns. (1) and (2), the free carrier density is

$$n_c = N_c \exp (-E_f/kT) \exp \{VCl(n_t se kT)\} \quad (3)$$

$$= n_{c0} \exp (\alpha V) \quad (4)$$

where n_{c0} is the initial thermal equilibrium concentration of free carriers and $\alpha = Cln_t se kT$.

The density of trapped carriers is very nearly equal to the total density of injected electrons, which is

$$Q/se = VCl(se) \quad (5)$$

From eqns. (3), (4) and (5), the fractional value of free charge is

$$\Theta = (en_{c0}/VC) \exp \alpha V \quad (6)$$

indicating the exponential dependence of Θ on the applied voltage.

If the steepness of the trap distribution⁶ is approximated by a characteristic temperature T_c such that

$$n_t \propto \exp (-E/(kT_c))$$

where E is measured from the bottom of the conduction band, small values of T_c lead to trap distribution varying rapidly with energy, while large values of T_c approximate to a slowly varying distribution.

The voltage dependence of space charge limited current is (for $T_c > T$) is

$$J \propto V^{TC/T-1}$$

which indicates that the current increases more rapidly with the applied voltage than in the case of the trap-free or discrete trap-level cases.

The activation energies obtained from Fig. 1 for naphthalene is 0.062, for anthracene 0.023 and for phenanthrene 0.021 eV. The fall in activation energy from naphthalene to anthracene may be due to larger π -electron density in the latter, tending to level off with more fused rings such as in phenanthrene.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log J - 1/T$ for different samples (1) naphthalene, (2) phenanthrene and (3) anthracene

Experimental

The experimental cell⁵ consisted of two plane, parallel and circular electrodes made of aluminium. The lower electrode was fixed and the upper electrode rigidly attached to the central leg of a spherometer. It could be displaced and the displacement read with the help of the graduated disc of the spherometer. The lower fixed electrode was of a larger diameter than the movable upper one.

Naphthalene (B.D.H.) was purified by distillation (twice) under low pressure. It was then warmed in an air oven at 90° and the molten mass was poured into the cell (preheated to the same temperature) and both the

Note

electrodes were immersed in naphthalene. The electrodes were set at predetermined distances from each other. Alteration in the distance between the two electrodes was effected by heating the whole cell and thereafter adjusting the upper electrode.

Anthracene was recrystallised from benzene and left to dry in a vacuum desiccator for several days before use.

As anthracene has a higher melting point and tends to decompose at temperatures around the melting point, the method adopted for naphthalene could not be used here. A spherical die of a hollow cylindrical shape was constructed, whose inner diameter was the same as that of the fixed electrode. A tight fitting stainless steel plunger was fitted into the hollow space. The material was then taken into the hollow space, tapped in gently all around. The plunger was then fitted and the whole transferred to a Bramah press which applied pressure on the plunger upto one metric tonne. The resulting pellet was then placed in the cell.

Phenanthrene was purified in the same manner as anthracene and its pellet was also made in the same way.

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